

A Search-based Motion Planner utilizing a Monitoring Functionality for Initiating Minimal Risk Maneuvers

Kailin Tong¹, Selim Solmaz¹ and Martin Horn²

Abstract—A reliable automated driving system (ADS) needs to perform a minimal risk maneuver (MRM) in the case of disruption of normal driving tasks, e.g., when its perception system fails or is unreliable. One way to achieve this is by utilizing a real-time monitoring device/functionality to supervise the automated driving system status to initiate a MRM. As opposed to previous research on MRM planning or safe-stop planning, where a redundant planner is running, we solve this problem in a different direction. We propose a motion planning framework for MRM by extending the directed-graph map for normal driving conditions. In our implementation, the Monitoring device supervises the health and data quality of sensors and decides whether a MRM should be initiated. If a MRM is triggered, no additional planner is required but only one additional backup search graph for MRM is utilized. Hence, the planner redundancy is no longer necessary and the computation resources can be potentially relieved. We evaluated our approach both in normal driving as well as conditions with perception fault injections leading to MRM. Simulations utilizing the Autoware (architecture proposal) software stack [1] indicate that the proposed framework fulfills the deadline of 30 ms and provides increased reliability in ADS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous driving promises improved driving safety by eliminating human errors, as well as increased traffic efficiency by reduced road congestion and vehicle emissions [2, pp. 3–4]. A major obstacle for launching highly automated vehicles in the mass market is to ensure their safety and reliability, which directly affects their user acceptance. Highly automated driving (HAD) requires capability to detect and handle hazardous events to ensure safety. Such hazardous events may stem from multiple sources, such as perception system degradation as a result of internal failures or external conditions, or when the driver cannot take over the driving task in time.

The SAE J3016 [3] standard provides the taxonomy and definitions related to automated driving. According to this taxonomy, named SAE levels, the classification of autonomy are expressed between SAE Level-0 (no automation) to SAE Level-5 (full automation). According to the standard, starting from Level-3 (conditional automation) and above, crash mitigation and avoidance capability should be part of

the automated driving system. The recent UN-ECE ALKS Standard [4] on automated lane keeping systems defines emergency maneuvers to prevent an imminent collision, where any longitudinal deceleration greater than $5 m/s^2$ is considered to be emergency condition, which may or may not include steering intervention.

A real-time monitoring device or function (which shall be denoted as MonDev) consists of hardware and/or software tools for collecting and processing vehicle data continuously to observe the nominal behavior of a system. MonDev utilizes this information for identifying and predicting potential failures leading to functional disruptions. The failures can result from a variety of sources including systemic faults, performance degradation of components, environmental conditions and functional design deficiencies attributable to all abstraction levels of a vehicle and/or its system architecture. For HAD (SAE Level-3 and higher) such a MonDev solution can be used to initiate corrective response measures, particularly when the automated driving system is not able to cope with a given situation. Without losing generality, in this work the MonDev particularly supervises the degradation and failure of the perception module, and provides triggers to initiate a MRM.

The SAE J3016 standard [3] defines “Minimal Risk Maneuver” (MRM) as an automated procedure that is targeted at minimizing risks during driving. It also defines “Minimal Risk Condition” (MRC), as the state arrived after performing a MRM. For example, the stand-still state is a common MRC. Recently, the white paper “Safety First For Automated Driving” [5] extends these definitions and proposes additional MRMs, such as transition demand, limit function state, comfort stop, safe-stop, emergency stop and recovery. In the current paper, we focus particularly on safe-stop as the MRM, since most other MRMs can be realized by changing parameters (e.g., as in comfort stop). Some other MRMs on the other hand require additional state machines (e.g., transition demand and recovery), which are outside the scope of the current paper. As opposed to automatic emergency braking systems or MRMs as defined in [4], the events that activate safe-stop are normally not urgent. Even though system or component degradation happens, the automated driving system (ADS) can still operate normally in a short duration (e.g., 10 seconds).

Contributions of the current paper can be summarized as follows:

- In previous work, safe-stop planning requires a redundant planner. By contrast, we exploit the concept of MonDev and incorporate safe-stop planning into

* This work is financially supported by the project Architect (GA Nr. 877539), supported by ECSEL JU, Horizon2020 and the Austrian funding authority FFG, and by the COMET K2 Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies Program.

¹ K. Tong and S. Solmaz are with Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH, Inffeldgasse 21a, 8010 Graz, Austria. {kailin.tong, selim.solmaz}@v2c2.at

² M. Horn is with Institute of Automation and Control at Graz University of Technology, Inffeldgasse 21b, 8010 Graz, Austria. martin.horn@tugraz.at

nominal search-based motion planner framework by extending the search graph and by changing parameters. Thus the system complexity and overheads can be reduced.

- A question has not been sufficiently addressed in the previous work. If the safe-stop planner is triggered, shall the ego vehicle smoothly stop at the current lane, or shall it attempt to stop in a safe region, e.g., the road hard shoulder. We answer this question by exploiting the resolution completeness of graph search.
- A practical MonDev-based software architecture is proposed, which is able to be deployed on car.

In what follows, we give first a recent literature review on the topic in Section-II and then introduce the system solution architecture in Section-III. The simulation implementation and the analysis of the results is eventually given in Section-IV followed by conclusions.

II. RELATED WORK

For an autonomous vehicle on a 2D plane, its configuration space consists of 3 dimensions: (x, y) for the position, and θ for the heading. However, to generate a kinematically/dynamically feasible trajectory, the additional time dimension and possibly other dimensions have to be considered. Many researches have attempted to solve this high-dimensional optimization problem with different state space descriptions, as surveyed in [6], [7]. For the tools and software platforms supporting trajectory planning, the interested reader is referred to [8].

One promising branch of motion planning is the spatio-temporal planning, which is advantageous in a dynamic environment. In light of formulating the planning problem, naively adding time and velocity dimensions causes a blow-up in the size of the search space. One approach to simplify the problem is decoupling the path planning and speed planning. An application example is the Baidu EM planner, in which path and speed are iteratively optimized [9]. Another direction for reducing the complexity is discretization of the search space. McNaughton et al. [10] proposed conformal spatio-temporal lattices to represent search space in structured environments. Their lattice vertices are connected by smooth curvature spirals along with different constant accelerations. Lattice planners provide robustness in different scenarios, however, it might be computationally expensive to repeatedly construct lattices in dynamics environments. A recent work tried to augment this approach by integrating an Intelligent Driver Model (IDM) as a speed feedback policy into lattice search [11]. Consequently it only requires spatial lattices but loses some flexibility.

Motion planning for MRM received so far limited focus of research, and has been mainly aimed at safe-stopping solutions. To demonstrate the benefit of a safe-stop planning, for example, the perception system is assumed to degrade or fail, hence the nominal motion planning cannot proceed, and a MRM is planned by another safe-stop planner. One notable work is the contingency planner proposed by Salvado [12]. A discrete set of motion primitives are generated offline,

and used in online search. It can provide a solution in short time frames (0.1s) thanks to an obstacle sensitive heuristic, however, the algorithm does not have a specific stop goal. Similarly, Svensson et al. formulated the safe-stop planning as an optimal control problem and calculated a set of trajectories offline [13]. The subset related to the current state is selected online and a lowest cost trajectory is opted for safe-stop. The algorithm is only validated in straight road, and it is difficult to cover all possible initial states. Recently, Wang et al. [14] address this issue by using an independent hierarchical planning architecture for safe-stop. A set of candidate paths are firstly generated in a Frenet frame using piecewise quintic polynomials and an optimal one among candidates is selected. Next, the dynamical obstacles are projected onto the selected path and a length-time (ST) graph is hence formulated. Finally, the velocity planning is realized by combining an extended hybrid A* search algorithm and quadratic programming. The results are validated in different simulation scenarios in presence of dynamic objects. However, this work introduces a complex software pipeline, and only considers the case of safe-stop on the hard shoulder.

Another interesting branch of fail-safe motion planning is based on a different assumption. The perception system remains reliable, but the intention of another vehicle changes, therefore a hazardous situation might occur and a MRM is required. Most recently, Pek and Althoff propose a fail-safe motion planner using online verification and convex optimization, and their approach presents real-time capability and safety assurance in real driving experiments. However, the research scope is different from ours.

Nevertheless, some problems still remain open for safe stop planning regarding perception system failure in [12], [13], [14], where a redundant planning system increases the system complexity. This potentially introduces more overheads. Hence, we attempt to embed the safe-stop planning into the nominal planning system. In addition, decision making for safe-stop in the current lane or in the safe-stop region is not well answered in the previous work.

III. PLANNING SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we give the big picture of the proposed software architecture and elaborate on its components.

A. Overall software architecture

Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed system architecture. The road geometry and the safe-stop zone (hard shoulder) are extracted from the lanelet2 map [15] to generate two directed-graph maps, one for normal driving conditions and one for MRM. Next, the ego position as well as the current and predicted positions of other traffic participants are projected onto the directed graph maps at each prediction time step. These maps are then used for generating a predictive directed-graph map for normal driving conditions as well as a backup map for MRM.

The constructed predictive directed-graph maps are further utilized by the graph search algorithm for collision

Fig. 1. Illustration of the proposed software architecture. Our contributions are in black frames, while dotted frames represent the Autoware software stack.

checks. The real-time MonDev executes system diagnosis and decides whether ADS operates in a normal state or in a MRM. If a MRM is triggered, the search algorithm switches from the normal search graph to the MRM search graph and utilizes those parameters configured for MRM. The final trajectory from the search algorithm is passed to the trajectory tracking controller of the Autoware software stack to drive the ego vehicle to the desired state.

In this work, the motion planning for normal driving conditions operates in a scheme of Receding Horizon Control (RHC), which re-plans at a fixed cycle time to make full use of the latest ego and traffic state. The re-planning frequency is 10 Hz. During a MRM, once the ego velocity is smaller than a predefined value, the re-planning stops and no new trajectory is planned. In the following sections, each component of the proposed framework is introduced.

B. Real-time monitoring device (MonDev)

In the context of the ADS, the real-time MonDev intended in this paper is a device/function that aims to reduce the residual risks. The underlying principle of the MonDev is to detect the onset of failure in the ADS as early as possible for ensuring maximum utilization of the system. The main goal of the MonDev is therefore to decide; 1) if a fault in the ADS exist and, 2) if so, whether the fault exceeds a certain risk threshold. If the risk threshold is exceeded, the MonDev triggers a MRM.

The conditions for fault detection is strongly dependent on the specific use case and implementation. In the context of the EU-ECSEL Project ArchitectECA2030 [16] an ADS with SAE Level-3 driving functions will be implemented for analysing the effect of fault propagation throughout the ADS. For this purpose, specific sensor failure types will be synthetically implemented including loss of a sensor, reduction in sensor signal quality and excessive number of signal dropout rates. A cumulative risk calculation function based on combination of these failure types and risk factors is then used for deciding whether a MRM condition is reached. For the sake of brevity, the detailed discussion of how the MonDev risk calculation is made is left out this paper. In the following simulations, the MRM condition will be triggered

by injecting a systematic failure.

C. Directed-graph map

Fig. 2. Construction of directed-graph maps

In this work, the directed-graph model proposed in [11] is used to represent the structured environment and to further support the execution of lattice search. It satisfies fundamental requirements for a map for planning algorithms: 1) represent the road geometry; 2) encompass traffic semantics and traffic rules. 3) be generated, updated (including extension and shortening) and retrieved efficiently.

We adopt Frenet frame representation for the directed map model. In a Frenet frame, the space is decoupled into two orthogonal axes s and l for lateral and longitudinal direction [17]. In our work, we use the center line of the right-most lane as the reference line and the directed graph is laid out in s and l axle.

A directed graph consists of directed edges and vertices. Vertices are waypoints including position, orientation, and curvature and are regularly sampled along center line of each possible lane. The directed edges describe the connectivity between vertices, The sampled vertices and directed edges for normal driving conditions are shown in Figure 2(a). It is assumed that an available safe-stop zone is provided by

the HD map as well, such as the hard shoulder of a road, as depicted as yellow vertices in Figure 2(a). The safe-stop zone is not considered in nominal driving but is incorporated in the search graph for MRM.

Construction of a directed-graph map is based on the interfacing with the Lanelet2 map file. The directed-graph map for nominal driving is constructed by the center lines of each lane, and by modeling the hard shoulder with vertices and directed edges, the directed-graph map for MRM is constructed and used as backup graph for MRM.

The occupancy of ego or other vehicles can be registered in the directed-graph map. To obtain directed-graph maps in future time steps (also named predictive directed-graph map), a behavior prediction model is necessary. The map-based prediction model from Autoware is used in our work. It predicts the possible trajectory at each time step of each agent based on the road geometry assuming a constant velocity. By exploiting the current and future information, an example of directed-graph map for current time step (initial time step for planning) and for the prediction time step k within the prediction horizon are shown in Fig. 2(c) and Fig. 2(d) respectively.

D. Search-based Motion Planning

In previous work, the fail-safe operation or MRM is separated differently from normal driving tasks and requires an additional motion planner. In our work, we propose a universal search-based motion planner for both MRM and normal driving scenarios. If a MRM is triggered, the backup directed-graph map for MRM is utilized, the cruise velocity and the desired lane is manipulated for a safe-stop. The MonDev regulates whether the ego vehicle is in normal operation or in MRM.

This work follows a similar search scheme as spatiotemporal lattice planner in [10], [11], and applies a Dijkstra search as well. The induction of time uses a grid approximation in the same spirit of Hybrid A* search. The major adaptations for our specific use cases will be elaborated in the following sections.

Fig. 3. Illustration of motion primitives. The red paths are motion primitives. Δs and Δl are the length of the longitudinal and lateral edges. s_{exp} is the length in longitudinal direction in one expansion. P_0 , P_1 and P_2 are vertices.

1) *Motion primitives*: Each vertex (also named as station) in a directed-graph map is defined as $P(n_s, n_l)$. n_s represents the vertex index in the longitudinal direction, and n_l

denotes the vertex index in the lateral direction. The position, orientation and curvature in a Cartesian frame are stored in each vertex, which is defined as $P(n_s, n_l) = [x, y, \theta, \kappa]$.

Motion primitives are the paths connecting vertices, as shown in Fig. 3. For a motion primitive executing lane change, we use a cubic polynomial spiral to denote the path, which is defined as:

$$\kappa(\tilde{s}) = a + b\tilde{s} + c\tilde{s}^2 + d\tilde{s}^3 \quad (1)$$

where the curvature of the path $\kappa(\tilde{s})$ is a cubic polynomial function of the arc length \tilde{s} .

The curvature $\kappa(\tilde{s})$ is optimized using the numerical optimization approach in [11]. Differently, the motion primitive for lane keeping is directly generated by interpolating the passed waypoints, as the lane center line already provides a reference path.

2) *Search graph*: In this paper, we use a discrete search space (s, l, v) . States s and l are the longitudinal length and lateral offset in the Frenet frame. v is the discretized ego velocity and is naturally constrained by the discretization range. N_s , N_l and N_v are the size of discretization for (s, l, v) respectively. The previous work [10] uses accelerations in the search space and claims it generates more variants of velocities. However, to make a full stop simpler, the dimension of acceleration is discarded in our work and only the velocity at each station is varied. As shown in Fig. 4, the out-degree of a node is $N_l N_v$. Hence, the total number of possible trajectories for the search graph is $O((N_l N_v)^{N_s})$.

The search graph is built upon the directed-graph map, as shown in Fig. 4. To avoid confusion, the term "node" now refers to vertices in a search graph. Each node is defined as: $N(n_s, n_l, n_v) = [x, y, \theta, \kappa, v, \tilde{s}, t, \bar{a}]$. n_s and n_l are the longitudinal and lateral indices in the aforementioned directed-graph map. n_v is the index for discretized velocity. \tilde{s} is the arc length of a motion primitive and t is the travel time on a motion primitive. As the arc length \tilde{s} is known from the motion primitive, the average longitudinal acceleration in the vehicle frame and the travel time can be induced from the initial state and final state.

Fig. 4. Illustration of a search graph and possible trajectories. It shows the motion primitives starting from node N_0 created for a road with N_l lanes. The vertical dash lines mark discretized layers in the longitudinal direction. The total number of possible trajectories ending on one layer is marked on the top of that layer.

3) *Cost function*: Inspired by control theory, the cost function of our search algorithm consists of penalties for deviation from the desired velocity and acceleration. To motivate the ego vehicle to drive along the desired lane, a penalty for deviation from the desired lane is added into the

cost. So the cost for expanding a node is defined as:

$$cost = w_1(v - v_d)^2 + w_2\bar{a}^2 + w_3|n_l - l_d| \quad (2)$$

where v is the velocity, v_d is the desired velocity, \bar{a} is the average longitudinal acceleration in the vehicle frame, n_l is the lane index, l_d is the desired lane index, and w_1 , w_2 and w_3 indicate positive tuning parameters.

The desired velocity is expressed as

$$v_d = \min\{v_c, \sqrt{a_{lat}^{des}/k(s)}\} \quad (3)$$

where v_c is a user-defined cruise velocity, a_{lat}^{des} is the desirable lateral acceleration in the vehicle frame, and $k(s)$ is the curvature of the motion primitive in a Cartesian frame.

If a MRM is triggered by the real-time MonDev, v_d is set to a minimal value for safe-stop and the l_d is set to 0, as the possible safe-stop zone is the right most lane.

4) *Node Expansion and pruning*: We follow the expand function in [10], [11], which expands the node in the longitudinal and lateral direction. The average longitudinal acceleration and travel time in one branch is induced by the initial and final node. When expanding a node, the branches causing collisions are removed. The collision check is implemented for the relevant nodes of a branch, which are defined in Fig. 5. If a relevant node of a branch is occupied by obstacles in the predictive directed-graph map between the start node time step and end node time step, that branch is pruned. Additionally, the branch whose average longitudinal acceleration exceeds a limit is also forbidden.

Fig. 5. Illustration of the relevant nodes for collision check. The relevant nodes for a lane change expansion are bounded in a blue dashed box, while the relevant nodes for a lane keeping expansion are bounded in a purple dashed box.

In our search scheme, once an expanded node has states exceeding s_{max} or t_{max} , the search is stopped and provides a solution as a sequence of paths along with a velocity at each station. The next step is to get smooth continuous velocity profiles along the generated paths, which is elaborated in the following section.

E. Velocity profile generation

The path provided by the search algorithm can be viewed as a 1D manifold. Assuming that there are m waypoints, we use cubic polynomials to connect discrete velocities at each waypoint, which is defined as:

$$v(\tilde{s}) = \begin{cases} v_1(\tilde{s}) = \sum_{i=0}^3 p_{1,i}\tilde{s}^i & \tilde{S}_0 \leq \tilde{s} \leq \tilde{S}_1 \\ v_2(\tilde{s}) = \sum_{i=0}^3 p_{2,i}\tilde{s}^i & \tilde{S}_1 \leq \tilde{s} \leq \tilde{S}_2 \\ \vdots \\ v_m(\tilde{s}) = \sum_{i=0}^3 p_{m,i}\tilde{s}^i & \tilde{S}_{m-1} \leq \tilde{s} \leq \tilde{S}_m \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In the equation 4, $p_{k,i}$ is the i^{th} order coefficient for the k^{th} segment of polynomial, \tilde{s} is the arc length of the path, and \tilde{S}_k is the arc length for the k^{th} waypoint. Next, we generate a smooth velocity profile along the path by minimizing the sum of squared $\partial^2 v / \partial \tilde{s}^2$. The speed profile generation in a 1D manifold is formulated as a constrained Quadratic Programming (QP) problem, following the method proposed in [18]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_m} & \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{p}_m \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} Q_1(\tilde{S}_1) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_m(\tilde{S}_m) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{p}_m \end{bmatrix} \\ \text{s.t.} & A_{eq} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{p}_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{d}_m \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In this expression, \mathbf{p}_i is the coefficient vector of the cubic polynomial describing the i^{th} segment. $Q_i(\tilde{S}_k)$ is the Hessian matrix for the k^{th} segment. A_{eq} is a mapping matrix. \mathbf{d}_k is a vector containing the k^{th} segment's derivative values for the beginning (d_0) and the end ($d_{\tilde{s}}$).

Luckily, the aforementioned constrained QP can be converted to an unconstrained QP, and solved directly for endpoint derivatives instead of polynomial coefficients. The optimal closed-form solution is written as [18]:

$$\mathbf{d}_P^* = -R_{PP}^{-1} R_{FP}^T \mathbf{d}_F \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{d}_F is a grouped vector of specified derivatives, and \mathbf{d}_P is a grouped vector of unspecified derivatives. R_{PP} and R_{FP} are intermediate matrices for calculation.

The smooth speed profile can be subsequently recovered from the resulting derivatives.

IV. EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the proposed approach in urban scenarios. Our proposed motion planning framework is implemented in C++ based on Robot Operation System (ROS) with a computer equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) W-2123 CPU @ 3.60GHz. In our simulation, the discrete longitudinal distance Δs is 2 m, and the longitudinal expansion distance $s_{exp} = 12 \Delta s$, which is 24 m. The s_{max} and t_{max} are 100 m and 10 seconds respectively. The longitudinal acceleration range is $[-3.0, 2.0] m/s^2$. In the following sections, we detail how the simulation scenarios are created, and demonstrate qualitative and quantitative results in the use cases described in Section IV-A.

A. Simulation environment

In order to get more realistic simulations, we use the simulation packages offered by the Autoware software stack, where measurement noises, localization errors as well stochastic agent behavior are available. An internally developed tool – ViFWare, functions as the interface among autonomous driving functions, simulators, maps, sensors and actuators. We use the "ideal twist" vehicle model of Autoware, and personalize it with the parameters of our

Fig. 6. Illustration of the Use Case 2 and 3. The strip is the planned trajectory. The color of it indicates velocity. White color indicates low velocity and red color indicates high velocity. The green rectangle denotes the simulated agents and the green circles are the predicted trajectory of the agent. On the top of the image, the steering angle and velocity of the ego vehicle are marked.

experiment vehicle. Although "ideal twist" model neglects vehicle dynamics and time delay effects, it is sufficient to demonstrate our concept of the motion planning framework.

The map we used here is the lanelet2 map of Carla Town 03 from open-source Carla Simulator [19], which consists of 2 lanes traveling in the same direction and curvy roads for urban environments. We design use cases as follows to validate the functionality of motion planning for normal driving conditions as well as MRM:

1) *Use Case 1: Normal driving conditions:* This use case is aimed at demonstrating the normal driving conditions for the ego car. We simulate 5 agents around the ego vehicle, including 3 slow agents (with maximal velocity of 10 km/h) and 2 relatively quicker agents (with maximal velocity of 18 km/h). If no perception error occurs, the ego vehicle is able to implement overtaking and drive on the curvy road without any collision. Due to the space limit, this use case is only shown in the attached video.

2) *Use Case 2: safe-stop in the current lane:* Fig. 6(a) shows one possibility for MRM: safe-stop in the current lane. The ego vehicle firstly drives in the left lane using the normal search graph. When the ego vehicle drives next to a simulated agent, a system failure is injected and the MRM is triggered by the real-time MonDev. At that moment, there is no safe distance to implement a lane change. Therefore, the ego vehicle decelerates and stops in the current lane.

3) *Use Case 3: safe-stop on the hard shoulder:* In the third Use Case, the ego vehicle drives in the left lane and passes two slow agents. At 10 seconds, a system failure is then injected and the real-time MonDev triggers MRM. Correspondingly, the search algorithm switches to the backup search graph for MRM. As there is enough space to safely change to the right lane, a reference trajectory towards the hard shoulder is planned and tracked by the ego vehicle. Finally the ego vehicle stands still on the hard shoulder, as shown in 6(b).

Fig. 7 shows the change of velocity in Use Case 3. At the beginning, the ego vehicle drives at about 13 m/s. At 10 seconds, a MRM is triggered, and the ego vehicle decelerates to 2 m/s in roughly 5 seconds. In Fig. 8, we compare the

Fig. 7. Variation of the ego vehicle velocity in Use Case 3 where MRM decision at $t=10s$ is indicated with a vertical line.

real motion of the ego vehicle with the planned trajectory. It can be seen that only minor tracking errors exist during the safe-stop maneuver. The ego car stops before the end of the planned trajectory, this is because that the velocity profile of the final part of the trajectory is nearly zero and the trajectory tracking controller filters the minimal target velocity.

B. Real-time performance

We implemented a worst-case time analysis for Use Case 2 and 3, as the real-time capability is critical for MRM. The worst-case search time, speed profile generation time and search graph update time are listed in Table I. Particularly, graph search dominates the runtime. To ensure a quick response to a perception system failure, the required deadline for the MRM planning is the control period, which is 30 ms. The worst-case total calculation time (15.03 ms) sufficiently meets this requirement. Therefore the proposed motion planning framework is plausibly able to run on embedded hardware with limited computation power.

Fig. 8. Planned and actual trajectories of the ego vehicle in Use Case 3.

TABLE I
WORST-CASE TIME PERFORMANCE FOR MOTION PLANNING

Search	Speed profile generation	Graph update	Total
10.68 ms	2.92 ms	1.43 ms	15.03 ms

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, we propose a novel monitoring-based software architecture and a motion planning algorithm which is capable of realizing both normal driving state and MRM. The real-time monitoring device supervises the ADS and triggers MRM. The search-based motion planning is extended to provide MRM planning, which only requires an additional backup search graph. Therefore no redundant planner for MRM is needed and the system complexity can be reduced. We validated the proposed approach in the Autoware software stack and it shows that it can cope with difficult situations. The worst-case calculation time for our proposed approach meets the requirement of control period (30 ms).

It is worth noting that, as the hardware is different, it is difficult to compare our calculation time with that of a system consisting of a redundant planner, such as [12], [13], [14]. We plan to reproduce the previous work on our platform for a better benchmark. Furthermore, in the simulation the other vehicles are driving in a constant speed. In the future, we will create more variant scenarios to test the robustness of the proposed MRM planner. Finally, a more complex vehicle motion model can be used during trajectory generation to extend the operational design domain.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The publication was written at Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH within the scope of the EU project ArchitectECA2030 and under grant agreement No 877539. The project is co-funded by grants from Germany, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Austria, Norway and - Electronic Component Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking (ECSEL JU). The authors would like to further acknowledge the financial support within the COMET K2 Competence Centers for

Excellent Technologies from the Austrian Federal Ministry for Climate Action (BMK), the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs (BMDW), the Province of Styria (Dept. 12) and the Styrian Business Promotion Agency (SFG). FFG has been authorised for the programme management.

REFERENCES

- [1] TierIV. (2022) Autoware (architecture proposal). [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/tier4/AutowareArchitectureProposal.proj>
- [2] D. Watzel and M. Horn, *Automated Driving*. Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- [3] SAE International, "Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles," Society of Automotive Engineers, USA, Standard SAE-J3016, Apr 2021.
- [4] United Nations, "Uniform provisions concerning the approval of vehicles with regard to Automated Lane Keeping Systems," Economic Commission for Europe, Geneva, CH, Standard ECE/TRANS/WP.29/2020/81, Apr 2020.
- [5] "Safety first for automated driving," Tech. Rep., Sep 2019.
- [6] S. Dixit, S. Fallah, U. Montanaro, M. Dianati, A. Stevens, F. McCullough, and A. Mouzakitis, "Trajectory planning and tracking for autonomous overtaking: State-of-the-art and future prospects," *Annual Reviews in Control*, vol. 45, pp. 76–86, 2018.
- [7] W. Schwarting, J. Alonso-Mora, and D. Rus, "Planning and decision-making for autonomous vehicles," *Annual Review of Control, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 187–210, 2018.
- [8] K. Tong, Z. Ajanovic, and G. Stettinger, "Overview of tools supporting planning for automated driving," in *2020 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [9] H. Fan, F. Zhu, C. Liu, L. Zhang, L. Zhuang, D. Li, W. Zhu, J. Hu, H. Li, and Q. Kong, "Baidu apollo em motion planner," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.08048*, 2018.
- [10] M. McNaughton, C. Urmson, J. M. Dolan, and J.-W. Lee, "Motion planning for autonomous driving with a conformal spatiotemporal lattice," in *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 09.05.2011 - 13.05.2011, pp. 4889–4895.
- [11] Ke Sun, Brent Schlotfeldt, Stephen Chaves, Paul Martin, Gulshan Mandhyan, and Vijay Kumar, "Feedback enhanced motion planning for autonomous vehicles," in *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), October 25-29, 2020, Las Vegas, NV, USA*, 2020.
- [12] J. Salvado, L. M. Custodio, and D. Hess, "Contingency planning for automated vehicles," in *2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 10/9/2016 - 10/14/2016, pp. 2853–2858.
- [13] L. Svensson, L. Masson, N. Mohan, E. Ward, A. P. Brenden, L. Feng, and M. Torngren, "Safe stop trajectory planning for highly automated vehicles: An optimal control problem formulation," in *2018 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*. IEEE, 62018, pp. 517–522.
- [14] Jingke Wang, Yue Wang, Dongkun Zhang, Yezhou Yang, and Rong Xiong, "Learning hierarchical behavior and motion planning for autonomous driving," in *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), October 25-29, 2020, Las Vegas, NV, USA*, 2020.
- [15] F. Poggenhans, J.-H. Pauls, J. Janosovits, S. Orf, M. Naumann, F. Kuhnt, and M. Mayr, "Lanelet2: A high-definition map framework for the future of automated driving," in *2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1672–1679.
- [16] ArchitectECA2030. (2020) Trustable architectures with acceptable residual risk for the electric, connected and automated cars. [Online]. Available: <https://architect-eca2030.eu/>
- [17] M. Werling, J. Ziegler, S. Kammel, and S. Thrun, "Optimal trajectory generation for dynamic street scenarios in a frenet frame," in *2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 03.05.2010 - 07.05.2010, pp. 987–993.
- [18] C. Richter, A. Bry, and N. Roy, "Polynomial trajectory planning for aggressive quadrotor flight in dense indoor environments," in *Robotics Research*, ser. Springer Tracts in Advanced Robotics, M. Inaba and P. Corke, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2016, vol. 114, pp. 649–666.

- [19] A. Dosovitskiy, G. Ros, F. Codevilla, A. Lopez, and V. Koltun, “Carla: An open urban driving simulator,” in *Conference on robot learning*. PMLR, 2017, pp. 1–16.